

Service Quality and Antenatal Care Visit Frequency at Klinik Utama Kehamilan Sehat in Bandung and Jakarta: A Comparative Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Perceived service quality may influence the use of antenatal care services. This comparative cross-sectional study compared perceived service quality and antenatal care visit frequency at Klinik Utama Kehamilan Sehat (KUKS) Jalan Peta, Bandung, and KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta. A total of 400 pregnant women were recruited, comprising 200 participants from each clinic. Perceived service quality was measured using a 26-item SERVQUAL-based questionnaire. Service-quality scores were compared using the Mann–Whitney U test, visit-frequency categories using the chi-square test, and dimension-specific associations using multiple linear regression. Overall service-quality scores were higher in Bandung than in Jakarta (97.92% vs. 90.42%; all SERVQUAL dimensions, $p < 0.001$). The proportion of participants reporting three or more antenatal care visits did not differ between Bandung and Jakarta (68.0% vs. 67.5%; $p = 0.915$). In Bandung, tangibles were negatively associated with visit frequency ($B = -0.303$; $p = 0.018$), whereas assurance was positively associated ($B = 0.562$; $p = 0.023$). In Jakarta, the overall regression model was not significant ($p = 0.118$). Perceived service quality was high at both clinics but higher in Bandung. Antenatal care visit frequency may be influenced by factors beyond perceived service quality, supporting branch-specific quality-improvement strategies.

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KEYWORDS: antenatal care; service quality; SERVQUAL; visit frequency; maternal health; cross-sectional study.

I. INTRODUCTION

High-quality health services and patient satisfaction are central indicators of health-facility performance because they reflect whether care is effective, safe, people-centred, and responsive to patients' needs and expectations (Alibrandi et al., 2023; World Health Organization, 2020). Service quality should therefore be continuously monitored and improved, as patients' needs, expectations, and evaluations of care may change over time in increasingly competitive health-care settings (Ali et al., 2024; Endeshaw, 2021). In maternal health care, women value not only clinical competence and safety but also respectful communication, clear information, timely responsiveness, supportive staff, and a comfortable care environment (Miller et al., 2021; Saetrum et al., 2024). Klinik Utama Kehamilan Sehat (KUKS), as a private maternity clinic network, provides a relevant setting to examine the relationship between perceived service quality and antenatal care visit frequency.

Previous studies have shown that perceived service quality is associated with patient satisfaction, trust, and continued use of health-care services (Chen et al., 2024; Shie et al., 2022;

Ubery & Ernawaty, 2024). The dimensions of responsiveness, reliability, tangibles, assurance, and empathy remain widely used to assess patients' perceptions of service quality, including in outpatient and primary-care services (Ali et al., 2024; Endeshaw, 2021). Patients who perceive care as timely, reliable, safe, empathetic, and well supported may be more likely to continue attending the same health-care facility. However, the frequency of antenatal care visits may also be influenced by factors beyond perceived service quality, including gestational age, clinical needs, access to care, scheduling, and individual patient circumstances.

Differences in patient perceptions between clinic branches may arise from variations in local patient characteristics, workforce performance, service processes, communication, waiting time, and physical facilities (Bergh et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2024). KUKS Duren Sawit in Jakarta and KUKS Jalan Peta in Bandung serve different urban populations and therefore provide an appropriate context for comparing perceived service quality and antenatal care visit frequency across branches. Both clinics operate within the Indonesian health-service framework, which emphasizes the provision,

supervision, and quality improvement of health facilities and health services. A comparative evaluation may help identify whether perceived service quality and antenatal care visit frequency differ between the two branches.

Therefore, this study aimed to compare perceived service quality and antenatal care visit frequency among women attending KUKS Duren Sawit in Jakarta and KUKS Jalan Peta in Bandung. Specifically, the study sought to describe and compare perceived service-quality scores between the two clinics, examine the simultaneous and individual associations of service-quality dimensions with antenatal care visit frequency within each clinic, and compare the distribution of antenatal care visit categories between branches. The findings may support branch-specific quality-improvement strategies and strengthen patient-centred antenatal care services in Indonesia.

II. METHODS

A. Study Design and Setting

This study used a comparative cross-sectional design to assess perceived service quality and antenatal care visit frequency among pregnant women attending KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta, and KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung. Data were collected from January to December 2022.

The study compared service-quality scores and antenatal care visit frequency between both clinics and examined the associations between the five SERVQUAL dimensions and antenatal care visit frequency within each clinic.

B. Study Population and Participants

The study population comprised pregnant women of any age and parity who attended antenatal care services at KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta, or KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, during the study period. Participants were eligible if they attended antenatal care at either clinic, were willing to participate, and had an Android-based mobile phone capable of accessing the Google Forms questionnaire. Participants who declined participation or submitted incomplete questionnaires were excluded.

A total of 400 respondents were included in the final analysis, comprising 200 participants from KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, and 200 participants from KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta. An equal number of participants was included from each clinic to enable comparison between branches. Separate multiple linear regression analyses were conducted in each clinic using the five service-quality dimensions as independent variables and antenatal care visit frequency as the dependent variable.

C. Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured self-administered questionnaire distributed through Google Forms after participants completed their clinic visit. Eligible participants were informed about the study purpose, voluntary participation, and confidentiality of their responses before

completing the questionnaire. Electronic informed consent was obtained before data collection.

The questionnaire assessed perceived service quality and antenatal care visit frequency. Perceived service quality was measured using a questionnaire based on the SERVQUAL framework, comprising five dimensions: responsiveness, reliability, tangibles, assurance, and empathy. The instrument consisted of 26 items rated on a four-point Likert scale, with higher scores indicating more favourable perceptions of service quality.

The responsiveness dimension consisted of four items, reliability of five items, tangibles of eight items, assurance of five items, and empathy of four items. Domain scores and total service-quality scores were calculated by summing the relevant item responses. The possible total service-quality score ranged from 26 to 104.

Percentage scores were interpreted as very dissatisfied (25.00–43.75%), less satisfied (43.76–62.50%), satisfied (62.51–81.25%), and very satisfied (81.26–100.00%).

D. Outcome Variable

The dependent variable was antenatal care visit frequency, defined as the reported number of antenatal care visits made by each participant at the respective clinic. This variable was analysed as a continuous outcome in the multiple linear regression models.

For descriptive comparison between clinics, antenatal care visit frequency was also categorised into two groups: three or more antenatal visits and two or fewer antenatal visits. This categorisation was used only to describe the distribution of antenatal care visits between clinics and was not interpreted as a direct measure of patient loyalty.

E. Instrument Validity and Reliability

The validity of the service-quality questionnaire items was assessed using Pearson product-moment correlation. Items with statistically significant item-total correlations were considered valid.

Internal consistency reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. A Cronbach's alpha value of ≥ 0.70 was considered acceptable.

F. Statistical Analysis

Data were analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Service-quality scores were presented as mean \pm standard deviation, with median and minimum–maximum values also reported for comparisons between clinics.

Differences in perceived service-quality scores between the two clinics were analysed using the Mann–Whitney U test, while antenatal care visit frequency categories were compared using the chi-square test.

Associations between service-quality dimensions (responsiveness, reliability, tangibles, assurance, and empathy) and antenatal care visit frequency were assessed separately for each clinic using multiple linear regression.

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Results were reported as regression coefficients (B), 95% confidence intervals (CIs), and p-values. All tests were two-sided, and $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

III. RESULTS

A total of 400 pregnant women were included in the analysis, comprising 200 respondents from KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, and 200 respondents from KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta.

A. Perceived Service Quality at KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung

At KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, the overall perceived service-quality score was 20,367 out of a maximum possible score of 20,800, corresponding to 97.92%. According to the score-interpretation criteria used in this study, the overall service quality was categorised as very satisfied.

All five SERVQUAL dimensions were also categorised as very satisfied. Assurance had the highest percentage score (98.35%), followed by responsiveness (98.25%), reliability (97.85%), empathy (97.72%), and tangibles (97.63%). Detailed service-quality scores are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Perceived Service Quality Scores at KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung

Dimension	Actual Score	Maximum Score	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
Responsiveness	3,144	3,200	98.25	Very satisfied
Reliability	3,914	4,000	97.85	Very satisfied
Tangibles	6,248	6,400	97.63	Very satisfied
Assurance	3,934	4,000	98.35	Very satisfied
Empathy	3,127	3,200	97.72	Very satisfied
Total service quality	20,367	20,800	97.92	Very satisfied

B. Perceived Service Quality at KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta

At KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta, the overall perceived service-quality score was 18,807 out of a maximum possible score of 20,800, corresponding to 90.42%. According to the score-interpretation criteria used in this study, the overall service quality was categorised as very satisfied.

Among the five SERVQUAL dimensions, responsiveness had the highest percentage score (92.28%), followed by assurance (91.23%), empathy (90.81%), reliability (89.50%), and tangibles (89.36%). All dimensions were categorised as very satisfied. Detailed service-quality scores are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Perceived Service Quality Scores at KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta

Dimension	Actual Score	Maximum Score	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
Responsiveness	2,953	3,200	92.28	Very satisfied
Reliability	3,580	4,000	89.50	Very satisfied
Tangibles	5,719	6,400	89.36	Very satisfied
Assurance	3,649	4,000	91.23	Very satisfied
Empathy	2,906	3,200	90.81	Very satisfied
Total service quality	18,807	20,800	90.42	Very satisfied

C. Association Between Service-Quality Dimensions and Antenatal Care Visit Frequency at KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung

Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the associations between the five service-quality dimensions and the frequency of antenatal visits at KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung. Responsiveness, reliability, tangibles, assurance, and empathy were entered simultaneously into the model.

Among the service-quality dimensions, tangibles and assurance were significantly associated with antenatal care visit frequency. Tangibles showed a negative association with visit frequency ($B = -0.303$; 95% CI, -0.553 to -0.053 ; $p = 0.018$), whereas assurance showed a positive association ($B = 0.562$; 95% CI, 0.077 to 1.047 ; $p = 0.023$). Responsiveness, reliability, and empathy were not significantly associated with antenatal care visit frequency (all $p > 0.05$). Detailed regression results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Service-Quality Dimensions and Antenatal Care Visit Frequency at KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung

Variable	B	Standard Error	Standardized β	t	p-value	95% CI for B
Constant	-0.517	2.605	—	-0.199	0.843	-5.655 to 4.621
Responsiveness	0.147	0.251	0.071	0.586	0.559	-0.348 to 0.641
Reliability	-0.023	0.197	-0.016	-0.117	0.907	-0.411 to 0.365
Tangibles	-0.303	0.127	-0.303	-2.391	0.018	-0.553 to -0.053
Assurance	0.562	0.246	0.317	2.287	0.023	0.077 to 1.047
Empathy	-0.004	0.209	-0.002	-0.019	0.985	-0.415 to 0.407

Dependent variable: antenatal care visit frequency. B = unstandardized regression coefficient; CI = confidence interval.

D. Associations Between Service-Quality Dimensions and Antenatal Care Visit Frequency at KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta

Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the associations between the five service-quality dimensions and antenatal care visit frequency at KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta. Responsiveness, reliability, tangibles, assurance, and empathy were entered simultaneously into the model.

The overall regression model was not statistically significant ($F[5,194] = 1.781$; $p = 0.118$). The model

explained 4.4% of the variation in antenatal care visit frequency ($R^2 = 0.044$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.019$). In the adjusted model, responsiveness was negatively associated with antenatal care visit frequency ($B = -0.247$; 95% CI, -0.459 to -0.036; $p = 0.022$), whereas reliability, tangibles, assurance, and empathy were not significantly associated with antenatal care visit frequency. Given that the overall model was not statistically significant, the association for responsiveness should be interpreted cautiously. Detailed results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Service-Quality Dimensions and Antenatal Care Visit Frequency at KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta

Variable	B	Standard Error	Standardized β	t	p-value	95% CI for B
Constant	2.121	1.072	—	1.978	0.049	0.006 to 4.236
Responsiveness	-0.247	0.107	-0.258	-2.306	0.022	-0.459 to -0.036
Reliability	0.051	0.101	0.070	0.508	0.612	-0.148 to 0.250
Tangibles	-0.027	0.071	-0.059	-0.383	0.702	-0.167 to 0.113
Assurance	0.015	0.134	0.020	0.109	0.913	-0.250 to 0.279
Empathy	0.260	0.155	0.293	1.679	0.095	-0.045 to 0.565

Dependent variable: frequency of antenatal care visits. Model fit: $F(5,194) = 1.781$; $p = 0.118$; $R = 0.209$; $R^2 = 0.044$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.019$; standard error of the estimate = 1.54637.

E. Comparison of Perceived Service Quality Between Clinics

Perceived service-quality scores were compared between KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, and KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta, using the Mann-Whitney U test. All five SERVQUAL dimensions and the total service-quality score were significantly higher among respondents at

KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, than among those at KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta (all $p < 0.001$). The largest absolute difference in mean score was observed for tangibles (31.24 ± 1.65 in Bandung vs. 28.60 ± 3.38 in Jakarta). The overall mean service-quality score was 101.84 ± 4.81 in Bandung and 94.04 ± 10.06 in Jakarta. Detailed comparisons are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Comparison of Perceived Service-Quality Scores Between KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, and KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta

Service-quality dimension	KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung (n = 200)	KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta (n = 200)	P-value*
Responsiveness	15.72 ± 0.80 ; median 16.00 (11.00–16.00)	14.77 ± 1.63 ; median 16.00 (11.00–16.00)	< 0.001
Reliability	19.57 ± 1.13 ; median 20.00 (14.00–20.00)	17.90 ± 2.13 ; median 19.00 (14.00–20.00)	< 0.001
Tangibles	31.24 ± 1.65 ; median 32.00 (24.00–32.00)	28.60 ± 3.38 ; median 30.00 (24.00–32.00)	< 0.001

Service-quality dimension	KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung (n = 200)	KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta (n = 200)	P-value*
Assurance	19.67 ± 0.93; median 20.00 (15.00–20.00)	18.25 ± 2.10; median 19.00 (15.00–20.00)	< 0.001
Empathy	15.64 ± 0.95; median 16.00 (12.00–16.00)	14.53 ± 1.76; median 16.00 (12.00–16.00)	< 0.001
Total service quality	101.84 ± 4.81; median 104.00 (78.00–104.00)	94.04 ± 10.06; median 98.00 (76.00–104.00)	< 0.001

Values are presented as mean ± standard deviation; median (minimum–maximum); P-values were calculated using the Mann–Whitney U test.

F. Comparison of Antenatal Care Visit Frequency Categories Between Clinics

Antenatal care visit frequency categories were compared between KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, and KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta, using the chi-square test. Three or more antenatal care visits were reported by 136 participants (68.0%) in Bandung and 135 participants

(67.5%) in Jakarta. Two antenatal care visits or fewer were reported by 64 participants (32.0%) in Bandung and 65 participants (32.5%) in Jakarta.

There was no statistically significant difference in the distribution of antenatal care visit frequency categories between the two clinics (p = 0.915), as presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Comparison of Antenatal Care Visit Frequency Categories Between KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, and KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta

Antenatal care visit-frequency category	KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung (n = 200)	KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta (n = 200)	p-value*
Three or more antenatal care visits	136 (68.0)	135 (67.5)	0.915
Two antenatal care visits or fewer	64 (32.0)	65 (32.5)	

Values are presented as n (%); P-value was calculated using the chi-square test.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study found that perceived service quality was categorised as very satisfied at both KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, and KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta. However, all SERVQUAL dimensions and the overall service-quality score were significantly higher in Bandung than in Jakarta. Women’s evaluations of antenatal care may be influenced by respectful interactions, individualised communication, and responsiveness to their needs (Miller et al., 2021). Professional and relational competence of health-care providers, patient participation, and adequate information provision have also been associated with higher satisfaction with antenatal care (Saetrum et al., 2024). Communication with physicians, health education, privacy, staff attitudes, and facility conditions may further shape women’s assessments of antenatal services (Almutairi et al., 2024; Hibusu et al., 2024).

The higher perceived service-quality scores in Bandung should not be interpreted as direct evidence of better clinical effectiveness or maternal outcomes. Antenatal care quality is multidimensional and includes facility readiness, provider competence, communication, clinical processes, and the patient’s experience of care (Hibusu et al., 2024; Khatri et al., 2022). The SERVQUAL framework is widely used to assess health-service quality through responsiveness, reliability, tangibles, assurance, and empathy; however, patients’ ratings may vary according to their expectations and personal experiences (Jonkisz et al., 2022). Studies in outpatient and hospital settings have also shown that perceived quality and satisfaction may differ across facilities

because of service processes, staff performance, communication, and physical conditions (Alharbi, 2023; Duc Thanh et al., 2022). Therefore, unmeasured differences in patient characteristics, expectations, waiting time, and local service delivery may partly explain the differences observed between the two clinics.

Although perceived service-quality scores were significantly higher in Bandung, the distribution of antenatal care visit frequency categories did not differ significantly between Bandung and Jakarta. This result suggests that perceived service quality alone may not fully explain antenatal care visit frequency. Maternal health-care utilisation may also be influenced by education, socioeconomic status, pregnancy intention, parity, access to transportation, distance, affordability, and family support (Li et al., 2023). The receipt of quality antenatal care has also been associated with demographic, socioeconomic, and health-system factors, rather than service perceptions alone (Sserwanja et al., 2022). Clinical service components, consultation time, provider interaction, and travel time may influence satisfaction and service utilisation among pregnant women (Hussen & Worku, 2022). Long clinic waiting times may reduce satisfaction and act as a barrier to antenatal care utilisation (Abdus-salam et al., 2021; Baron & Kaura, 2021). Therefore, antenatal care visit frequency in this study should be interpreted as a service-utilisation indicator and not as a direct measure of patient loyalty.

At KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, tangibles and assurance were significantly associated with antenatal care visit frequency after adjustment for the other SERVQUAL

dimensions. The positive association between assurance and visit frequency may indicate that participants who reported greater confidence in staff competence, professional communication, safety, and clarity of information tended to have more frequent antenatal care visits. Respectful maternity care, counselling about pregnancy danger signs, and previous antenatal care experiences have been associated with maternal satisfaction in other settings (Ayalew et al., 2021). Maternal satisfaction has also been linked to the quality of provider communication, adequate information, and the perceived competence of health professionals (Bekele et al., 2023; Kebede et al., 2020). However, the negative coefficient for tangibles should not be interpreted as evidence that poorer physical facilities increase antenatal care visit frequency. Because the five SERVQUAL dimensions were entered simultaneously, this finding may reflect overlap among dimensions, differences in patient expectations, or unmeasured clinical and contextual factors.

At KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta, responsiveness was negatively associated with antenatal care visit frequency in the adjusted model. However, the overall regression model was not statistically significant and explained only 4.4% of the variation in antenatal care visit frequency. Therefore, this individual association should be interpreted cautiously and should not be regarded as evidence that lower responsiveness increases antenatal care visits. Responsiveness remains important because timely assistance, clear service flow, staff attention, and effective communication are central components of patient experience and satisfaction (Abdus-salam et al., 2021; Almutairi et al., 2024). Evidence from health-service research also indicates that perceived service quality may be associated with satisfaction and perceived value, although the importance of individual service dimensions may differ across clinical settings and patient populations (Duc Thanh et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2021).

The differing patterns between Bandung and Jakarta indicate that quality-improvement priorities may need to be tailored to each clinic branch. In Bandung, assurance-related improvement may include clearer communication about examination findings, pregnancy care plans, warning signs, and the roles of health professionals. In Jakarta, assessment of service flow may be relevant, including registration procedures, waiting time, communication during consultations, and coordination between administrative and clinical staff. Improvements in antenatal care should consider both structural and interpersonal components of care, including facility organisation, provider communication, patient education, and responsiveness to women’s concerns (Khatri et al., 2022). Alternative antenatal care models that combine clinical assessment, health education, and supportive interaction have also been associated with higher maternal satisfaction in several settings (Sadiku et al., 2024).

This study has several limitations. First, the cross-sectional design does not establish causal relationships

between perceived service quality and antenatal care visit frequency. Second, antenatal care visit frequency was self-reported and may have been affected by recall error. Third, important determinants of antenatal care utilisation, including gestational age, timing of the first antenatal visit, pregnancy risk, distance from the clinic, insurance status, cost, employment, and family support, were not measured. Fourth, data collection through Google Forms limited participation to women with access to Android-based mobile phones. Finally, the very high service-quality scores may have caused a ceiling effect and reduced the ability to identify variation in associations between individual SERVQUAL dimensions and antenatal care visit frequency.

V. CONCLUSION

Perceived service quality was high at both KUKS branches, although all SERVQUAL dimensions and the overall service-quality score were significantly higher at KUKS Jalan Peta, Bandung, than at KUKS Duren Sawit, Jakarta. The distribution of antenatal care visit-frequency categories did not differ significantly between the two clinics. In Bandung, tangibles and assurance were associated with antenatal care visit frequency. In Jakarta, responsiveness showed an individual association with visit frequency; however, the overall regression model was not statistically significant and should be interpreted cautiously. These findings indicate that antenatal care visit frequency may be influenced by factors beyond perceived service quality and support branch-specific quality-improvement strategies.

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REFERENCES

1. Abdus-salam, R., Adeniyi, A., & Bello, F. (2021). Antenatal Clinic Waiting Time, Patient Satisfaction, and Preference for Staggered Appointment—A Cross-Sectional Study. *Journal of Patient Experience*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23743735211060802>
2. Alharbi, M. F. (2023). Patients’ experience of service quality in government and private hospitals in the Qassim Region, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Medicine and Life*, 16(11), 1622–1627. <https://doi.org/10.25122/jml-2023-0184>
3. Ali, J., Jusoh, A., Idris, N., & Nor, K. M. (2024). Healthcare service quality and patient satisfaction: A conceptual framework. *International Journal of*

- Quality and Reliability Management, 41(2), 608–627. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-04-2022-0136>
4. Alibrandi, A., Gitto, L., Limosani, M., & Mustica, P. F. (2023). Patient satisfaction and quality of hospital care. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 97, 102251. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evalprogplan.2023.102251>
 5. Almutairi, G., Alshmrani, L. S., Alomairi, R. M., Alotaibi, M. S., Alhumaidi, N. H., Alotaibi, R. M., Aljebeli, S. M., Alarfaj, S. A., Alhenaki, S. A., Albedah, B. A., & Alhomaid, T. A. (2024). Assessment of pregnant women’s satisfaction with the model of care initiative: Antenatal care services at primary health care centers in the Qassim Health Cluster, Saudi Arabia. *Cureus*, 16(12), e76383. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.76383>
 6. Ayalew, M. M., Nebeb, G. T., Bizuneh, M. M., & Dagne, A. H. (2021). Women’s Satisfaction and Its Associated Factors with Antenatal Care Services at Public Health Facilities: A Cross-Sectional Study. *International Journal of Women’s Health*, Volume 13, 279–286. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJWH.S293725>
 7. Baron, J. C., & Kaura, D. (2021). Perspectives on waiting times in an antenatal clinic: A case study in the Western Cape. *Health SA Gesondheid*, 26. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hsag.v26i0.1513>
 8. Bekele, G. G., Seifu, B., & Roga, E. Y. (2023). Determinants of maternal satisfaction with focused antenatal care services rendered at public health facilities in the West Shewa Zone, Central Ethiopia: A multicentre cross-sectional study. *Frontiers in Global Women’s Health*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgwh.2022.902876>
 9. Bergh, K., Bishu, S., & Taddese, H. B. (2022). Identifying the determinants of patient satisfaction in the context of antenatal care in Kenya, Tanzania, and Malawi using service provision assessment data. *BMC Health Services Research*, 22, 746. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-022-08085-0>
 10. Chen, L.-H., Chen, C.-H., Loverio, J. P., Wang, M.-J. S., Lee, L.-H., & Hou, Y.-P. (2024). Examining soft and hard attributes of health care service quality and their impacts on patient satisfaction and loyalty. *Quality Management in Health Care*, 33(3), 176–191. <https://doi.org/10.1097/QMH.0000000000000420>
 11. Duc Thanh, N., My Anh, B. T., Xiem, C. H., Quynh Anh, P., Tien, P. H., Thi Phuong Thanh, N., Huu Quang, C., Ha, V. T., & Thanh Hung, P. (2022). Patient Satisfaction With Healthcare Service Quality and Its Associated Factors at One Polyclinic in Hanoi, Vietnam. *International Journal of Public Health*, 67. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ijph.2022.1605055>
 12. Endeshaw, B. (2021). Healthcare service quality-measurement models: A review. *Journal of Health Research*, 35(2), 106–117. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHR-07-2019-0152>
 13. Hibusu, L., Sumankuuro, J., Gwelo, N. B., & Akintola, O. (2024). Pregnant women’s satisfaction with the quality of antenatal care and the continued willingness to use health facility care in Lusaka district, Zambia. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 24, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-023-06181-5>
 14. Hussien, M. A., & Worku, B. T. (2022). Quality of Antenatal Care Service and Factors Associated with Client Satisfaction at Public Health Facilities of Bele Gasgar District. *Journal of Patient Experience*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23743735221083163>
 15. Jonkisz, A., Karniej, P., & Krasowska, D. (2022). The Servqual Method as an Assessment Tool of the Quality of Medical Services in Selected Asian Countries. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(13), 7831. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19137831>
 16. Kebede, D. B., Belachew, Y. B., Selbana, D. W., & Gizaw, A. B. (2020). Maternal Satisfaction with Antenatal Care and Associated Factors among Pregnant Women in Hossana Town. *International Journal of Reproductive Medicine*, 2020, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/2156347>
 17. Khatri, R. B., Mengistu, T. S., & Assefa, Y. (2022). Input, process, and output factors contributing to quality of antenatal care services: a scoping review of evidence. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 22(1), 977. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-022-05331-5>
 18. Li, Y., Li, H., & Jiang, Y. (2023). Factors influencing maternal healthcare utilization in Papua New Guinea: Andersen’s behaviour model. *BMC Women’s Health*, 23(1), 544. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-023-02709-1>
 19. Miller, P. A., Afulani, P. A., Musange, S., Sayingoza, F., & Walker, D. (2021). Person-centered antenatal care and associated factors in Rwanda: A secondary analysis of program data. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 21, 290. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-021-03747-z>
 20. Nguyen, N. X., Tran, K., & Nguyen, T. A. (2021). Impact of Service Quality on In-Patients’ Satisfaction, Perceived Value, and Customer Loyalty: A Mixed-Methods Study from a Developing Country. *Patient Preference and Adherence*, Volume 15, 2523–2538. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S333586>

“Service Quality and Antenatal Care Visit Frequency at Klinik Utama Kehamilan Sehat in Bandung and Jakarta: A Comparative Cross-Sectional Study”

21. Sadiku, F., Bucinca, H., Talrich, F., Molliqaj, V., Selmani, E., McCourt, C., Rijnders, M., Little, G., Goodman, D. C., Rising, S. S., & Hoxha, I. (2024). Maternal satisfaction with group care: a systematic review. *AJOG Global Reports*, 4(1), 100301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xagr.2023.100301>
22. Saetrum, A., Kaiser, S., & Martinussen, M. (2024). User satisfaction with antenatal care in Norway. *Birth*, 51(1), 89–97. <https://doi.org/10.1111/birt.12768>
23. Shie, A.-J., Huang, Y.-F., Li, G.-Y., Lyu, W.-Y., Yang, M., Dai, Y.-Y., Su, Z.-H., & Wu, Y. J. (2022). Exploring the relationship between hospital service quality, patient trust, and loyalty from a service encounter perspective in elderly with chronic diseases. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 876266. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.876266>
24. Sserwanja, Q., Nuwabaine, L., Gatasi, G., Wandabwa, J. N., & Musaba, M. W. (2022). Factors associated with utilization of quality antenatal care: a secondary data analysis of Rwandan Demographic Health Survey 2020. *BMC Health Services Research*, 22(1), 812. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-022-08169-x>
25. Ubery, Y. F., & Ernawaty, E. (2024). Determinants of patient loyalty: A systematic review. *MAHESA: Malahayati Health Student Journal*, 4(9), 4127–4147. <https://doi.org/10.33024/mahesa.v4i9.15612>
26. World Health Organization. (2020). Quality health services: a planning guide. World Health Organization, (July), 1–48. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/quality-health-services>